

The 12th International Scientific Conference
eLearning and Software for Education
Bucharest, April 21-22, 2016
10.12753/2066-026X-16-000

APPROACHING ASSESSMENT IN EDUCATIONAL GAMES

Antoniu Stefan, Ioana Andreea Stanescu

Advanced Technology Systems, 1 Tineretului Str., Târgoviște, Romania
antoni.stefan@ats.com.ro; ioana.stanescu@ats.com.ro

Jannicke Baalsrud Hauge

University of Bremen, Bremer Institut für Produktion und Logistik, Hochschulring 20, 28359, Bremen, Germany
jmbh@uni-bremen.de

Sylvester Arnab

Disruptive Media Learning Lab Coventry University, Coventry CV1 5FB, UK
s.arnab@coventry.ac.uk

Abstract: *The use of games in education necessitates investigations on how to successfully transpose learning objectives and evaluation metrics into game settings, how to effectively assess player performance in the game, and also on how to overcome technical issues associated with the integration of Digital Educational Games (DEG) and Learning Management Systems (LMS). According to Bloom's taxonomy, revised by Anderson in 2001, which is used to develop learning objectives, there are six categories in the cognitive process dimension that should be considered: remember, understand, apply, analyse, evaluate and create. Marzano and Kendall have proposed a new taxonomy (Fig. 1) that integrates three domains of knowledge - information, mental procedures, and psychomotor procedures - and six level of processing: retrieval, comprehension, analysis, knowledge utilization, metacognitive system, self-system. To construct DEGs that assess player's performance in connection with these categories constitute a challenge. Digital games are in essence complex artefacts, whose design and development require extensive efforts both from pedagogical and technical points of view. While methods common to an assessment content are core to many DEGs (rewards, levels, leader boards), creating game assessment mechanisms that are motivating and even disruptive from traditional evaluation methods, and yet can be integrated into formal evaluation processes is still subject to research. This paper examines the design and development of assessment mechanisms for a language learning game, with the purpose of identifying how various assessment mechanisms can be applied in game contexts. The authors also discuss technical issues associated with interconnecting games and LMSs, exploring the possibility to automatically upload assessment criteria into the game and integrate game assessment reports into the LMS. This approach targets to implement a new level of flexibility in game development processes, enabling tutors to customize the assessment mechanisms within the game.*

Keywords: *learning taxonomy, learning objective, LMS.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's students and employees have grown up with fast-paced, immersive, interactive media stimuli, and they are very practiced in tuning out boring experiences [1]. Digital Educational Games (DEGs) have emerged as an opportunity to motivate individuals to learn by engaging them in novel experiences. Even if the scope of DEGs is not to entertain, but to impart knowledge and expertise to the players, DEGs offer unique ways of engagement, they have been proven to be powerful learning tools [2, 3, 4].

However significant are the benefits they bring in education, due to the complex nature of the pedagogical approaches, designing DEGs is not an easy endeavour. Besides the challenges inherited from entertainment games [5], such as building rewarding experiences while playing, DEGs raise new provocations derived from their educational core. Additional to constructing a fun and rewarding experience for the player, DEG designers need to carefully address discipline specific pedagogical requirements. Therefore, unlike entertainment games that promise long term engagement across hundreds of levels, DEGs often have a very focused gameplay and they are often designed to be played in a few hours [3]. Successfully blending learning objectives and assessment mechanisms without sacrificing the fun represent a critical issue that requires special attention in the design phase.

Currently, the integration of DEGs at pedagogical level (into learning paths) and at technical level (into educational platforms) remains limited [6]. There are no automated connections between learning objectives and assessment metrics defined in the lesson plans and DEGs. Moreover, even if DEGs enable tracking of the player performance, the play outcomes are not automatically integrated into learning platforms. Such discontinuities generate significant obstacles in adopting DEGs as a long term practice.

In this context, this paper discusses key learning taxonomies in an effort to support the integration of learning objectives and assessment metrics into DEGs from both pedagogical and technic perspectives. The authors present a case study for Tingo, a game for foreign language learning that exemplifies the harmonization of game activities with learning objectives and the automated integration of play outcomes into learning platforms.

II. CONNECTING LEARNING AND GAMES

Bloom's taxonomy and others based on it [7] have brought a major contribution to the science of designing educational objectives. However, implementing these taxonomies when designing DEGs remains challenging. This section presents reference taxonomies that guide the design and assessment of educational objectives and discuss key learning theories, with the purpose on analysing their application in DEG design. A case study for a foreign language game is presented.

Bloom's taxonomy has considered three key learning domains: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor and it has built upon the notion that an educational objective should contain a clear reference to a specific type of knowledge, and also define the behaviours that would signal understanding or skill related to that specific knowledge. According to Bloom's taxonomy, revised by Anderson in 2001 [7], there are six categories in the cognitive process dimension that should be considered: remember, understand, apply, analyse, evaluate and create.

Figure 1. Marzano and Kendall Taxonomy [8]

Marzano and Kendall [8] have proposed a new taxonomy (Fig. 1) that integrates three domains of knowledge (information, mental procedures, and psychomotor procedures) and six level of processing: retrieval, comprehension, analysis, knowledge utilization, metacognitive system, self-system.

Starting from this new taxonomy proposed by [8], this paper correlates learning objectives identified under the first three levels of the taxonomy, respectively retrieval, comprehension, and analysis, with specific learning activities designed for the foreign language game Tingo.

Table 1. Transposing learning objectives into game activities

Taxonomy Level/ Operation	Learning objectives	Game activities
Level 1 Retrieval		
Recognizing	The player is able to validate correct statements, without necessarily understanding the structure of the knowledge or differentiate critical and noncritical components.	Choose the correct answer. True/ False exercises. Vocabulary exercises. Reading skills practice. Listening skills practice.
Recalling	The player is able to produce features of information, without necessarily understanding the structure of the knowledge or differentiating critical and noncritical components.	True/ False exercises Word formation Match words to pictures Match words to definition Word list recall Find the mistakes and correct them.
Executing	The player is able to perform a procedure without significant error, without necessarily understanding the structure of the knowledge or differentiating critical and noncritical components.	Type the correct form. Translate words. Read a text and identify compound words. Listen to a text and fill in the blanks.
Level 2 Comprehension		
Integrating	The player is able to identify the basic structure of the information, and differentiate critical and noncritical characteristics.	Fill in the blanks Word order in positive sentences Word order in negative sentences Word order in questions Word order in subordinate clauses Position of time expression
Symbolizing	The players is able to construct an accurate symbolic representation of the information, and differentiate critical and noncritical characteristics.	Translate simple and compound words. Translate idioms, idiomatic expressions, proverbs and sayings. Translate sentences. Phrasal verbs.
Level 3 Analysis		
Matching	The player is able to identify important similarities and differences concerning the	Choose the synonyms Fill in the antonyms Match symbols with the

	information.	correct instructions.
Classifying	The player is able to identify superordinate and subordinate categories concerning the information.	Comparison of adjectives Irregular plural Irregular verbs
Analysing Errors	The player is able to identify errors in the presentation or use of the information.	Identify mistakes in a written text. Correct the mistakes. Identify mistakes in a voice message.
Specifying	The player is able to identify logical consequences of the information.	Sequence of tenses. Translate complex texts. Listening skills practice.

The game scenarios for Tingo were built based on the curricula developed by the Romanian Ministry of Education and Scientific Research for the following areas: primary education; secondary education; high school. In the design phase, curricula for associated disciplines has also been considered: International Business and Economics; Applied Modern Languages; International development policy; Business communication in English; Communication in English for teaching and economic research; Diplomacy in the international economy, etc.

The flow charts below present the structures designed for practicing the plural form of nouns:

a. Level 1 Retrieval - Recognizing: The player chooses the answer from three alternatives (Fig 2). If the option chosen is correct, the player will receive one point. If the answer is incorrect, the player will not receive any points. The flowchart has a linear structure and the player cannot introduce a second answer.

b. Level 1 Retrieval - Executing; The player types the answer (Fig. 3). If the answer entered is correct, the player will receive one point. If the answer is incorrect, the player can choose to type another answer, quit the exercise or move on to the next sequence.

Fig. 2 Linear flowchart for Recognizing

Fig. 3 Opportunity flowchart for Executing

Based on the player performance, s/he will be awarded bonus resources that can be used to fulfil specific quests that enable the player to advance faster in the game. This mechanic aims to make the player more responsible when fulfilling game quests.

For example, to be able to construct the Pottery, the player needs to collect construction materials (Fig. 4). These materials can be obtained upon the completion of sets of tasks that address a blend of learning objectives falling under Level 1 – Retrieval and Level 2 – Comprehension. To obtain Resource 1 and Resource 2, the player need to choose the correct answer from a given set of questions (Level 1 Retrieval – Recognizing) and to translate simple and compound words (Level 2 Comprehension – Symbolizing). In this first step of the learning sequence, a picture of an abject and three versions of translation are displayed. To reinforce learning, all three words are correct. The version selected by the player is evaluated: if the answer is correct, the player moves to the next step;

if the answer is incorrect, the player returns to the previous step. This mechanic was chosen to allow the player to interact visually with text - image pairs and stimulate recognizing and recalling (Level 1).

Fig. 4. Collecting resources to build the pottery

Next, the player visualizes an image and needs to type the translation. The text typed by the player is evaluated: if the text is correct, the player moves to the next step; if the text is incorrect, then the player can access one of the following choices: (1) choose from translation options; (2) return to the previous step and type a new translation.

In the third step, the player is viewing two or more images and is able to choose or type the correct answer. If the answer is correct, the player moves to the next step; if selected/ typed answers are incorrect, then the player can access the same options as in step two.

For each milestone reached, the player is given additional resources.

III. ENABLING COMMUNICATION BETWEEN DEGs AND LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

To fully integrate DEGs in educational settings, connecting learning objectives with game assessment mechanisms does not suffice. Tracking player performance in DEGs and integrating it into platforms such as Learning Management Systems represent a necessary step, in order to fully streamline the implementation of DEGs in education. To enable communication between a DEG and an LMS, an Identity Management component has been developed.

The Identity Management component makes the connection between the DEG and external LMSs or other educational platforms that allow the authentication of the player, in order to establish the learning context and make the connection between a student and a character performing in the

virtual environment of the game. Given the general nature of identity management functionalities required for the players, these were grouped as a component that can be reused easily in other DEGs.

At the component level, in a first phase, the authentication can be done automatically based on a session identifier (token) automatically transmitted by the LMS or based on an access code introduced when the game is played for the first time. When the LMS is transmitting an identifier, the player is recognized automatically and the gaming experience can be automatically adjusted according to the information received from the LMS or from other sources. Thus, the Identity Management component can connect to a server that implements LDAP (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol) to identify the player and adapt the learning content based on this attribute, these transactions being made completely transparent for the player.

The component also enables user authentication using social network accounts by linking to their profile. The component can operate as a broker of information between the social profile of the player and other components of the game to allow them to use profile information to customize social learning mechanisms.

```
using UnityEngine;
using System.Collections;

public class CitesteBarem : MonoBehaviour
{
    // Adresa serviciului REST
    string adresaServiciu = "http://www.sgref.com/Servicii/Barem/Get/";

    IEnumerator Start()
    {
        // Cream formularul cu parametrii pentru POST
        WWWForm cerere = new WWWForm();
        // Token-ul primit la autentificare
        cerere.AddField("tokenAuth", Desig.Context.tokenAuth);
        // Numele jucatorului
        cerere.AddField("jucator", Desig.Context.jucator);

        // Trimitem cererea
        WWW raspuns = new WWW(adresaServiciu, cerere);

        yield return raspuns;
    }
}
```

The script above connects to a Learning Management System to retrieve a scoring scale that is used by the assessment component of the DEGs. Interconnecting DEGs with such systems facilitates the use of DEGs as examination tools, as well as integrating the game results into the student records.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper builds upon existing learning taxonomies and constructs guidelines for designing educational games that address specific learning objectives. Starting from Marzano and Kendall's taxonomy, the authors carry out a case study for a foreign language learning game and articulate game activities on learning objectives for three taxonomy levels: retrieval, comprehension and analysis. To support the full integration of DEGs into learning practices, an Identity Management component has been developed to integrate the game with Learning Management Systems, enabling the automatic collection of user data into learning platforms.

Future work will consider the interconnection of game activities with the remaining levels in the Marzano and Kendall's taxonomy: knowledge utilization, metacognitive system, and self-system. From the assessment perspective, the development efforts will focus on enabling the retrieval and integration at game level of assessment metrics defined by tutors in LMSs.

Acknowledgements

The work presented herein is partially funded under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union (BEACONING Project, Grant Agreement 687676) and Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea Invatamantului Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii (UEFISCDI, DESIG Project, Contract no. 19/2014).

References

- [1] Borst, T., Iuppa, N. 2012. *Story and Simulations for Serious Games*, Focal Press.
- [2] Duin, H., Cerinsek, G., Fradinho, M., Taish, M. 2012. Serious Gaming Supporting Competence Development in Sustainable Manufacturing. In *Handbook of Research on Serious Games as Educational, Business and Research Tools*, Cruz-Cunha M. (Ed.). IGI Global.
- [3] Duin, H., Baalsrud Hauge, J., Hunecker, F., Thoben, K.D. 2011. Application of Serious Games in Industrial Contexts. In *Business, Technological, and Social Dimensions of Computer Games*, Cruz-Cunha, M., Tavares, P., Varvalho, V. H. IGI Global.
- [4] Moreno-Ger, P., Baxter, G., Boyle, E., Hainey, T., Connolly, T. 2013. *Psychology, Pedagogy, and Assessment in Serious Games*. IGI Global.
- [5] deMaria, R., Perry, D. 2009. *David Perry on Game Design: A Brainstorming Toolbox*. Course Technology.
- [6] Stefan A., Stănescu, I. A., Roceanu, I., Banciu, D. 2014. A Walkthrough Serious Games Design & Development. ISI proceedings of the International Conference on Virtual Learning, Bucharest, Romania.
- [7] Anderson, L. W., Krathwohl, D.R., Airasian, P. W., Cruikshank K. A., Mayer R. E., Pintrich, P. R., Raths, J., Wittrock, M. C. 2001. *A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives*. Pearson.
- [8] Marzano, R. J., Kendall, J. S. 2008. *Designing and Assessing Educational Objectives: Applying the New Taxonomy*. Corwin.